

COVID-19 Stroke on Russia: Looking Forward for Future Development through Antibody Test Spectacles

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ABSTRACT

Natalia P. Sharova. *COVID-19 stroke on Russia: Looking forward for future development through antibody test spectacles.* On 9 June 2020, COVID-19-related quarantine measures were at last suspended in Moscow. Russian government claimed that an effective tool to predict future post-COVID-19 development of Russia would be mass screening of Russian population for antibodies to SARS-CoV-2. However, analysing the techniques used by Moscow and several other Russian local authorities to detect antibodies, we come to a conclusion that such screening is being performed ineffectively. An alternate has been proposed in the paper.

Key words: SARS-CoV-2, antibody test, mass screening, population screening, herd immunity, post-COVID social development

ON 9 JUNE 2020, COVID-19-RELATED QUARANTINE MEASURES were at last suspended in Moscow. Russian government claimed that an effective tool to predict future post-COVID-19 development of Russia would be mass screening of Russian population for antibodies to SARS-CoV-2. Indeed, such an information would help one to estimate how many people in Moscow and the whole of Russia are COVID-19 convalescents. In turn, those data would give an indication of time of opening borders, complete removal of quarantine measures and transition to a conventional way of life.

However, analysing the laboratory techniques used by Moscow and several other Russian local authorities to detect antibodies to SARS-CoV-2, we come to a conclusion that such screening is being performed ineffectively. In Russia, many administrative measures related to COVID-19 surveillance, prevention and treatment, have been ungrounded by preliminary epidemiological calculations or thorough analysis. Russian medical care system must have submitted to non-evidence-based orders of governmental officials and bureaucrats.

Since 14 May 2020, a program of wide serological screening of population was launched in Russia. As of 10 June 2020, three serological test systems are currently commercially available for Russian diagnostic community (The List 2020). They are produced by 1) Shenzhen Mindray Bio-Medical Electronics Co Ltd (China) (Russian registration licenses no. 2020/10269-10270 of May 07, 2020), 2) Vector-Best (Novosibirsk, Russia) (licenses no. 2020/10388-10389 of May 18, 2020) and 3) State Research Center for Applied Microbiology and Biotechnology (SRCAMB) (Obolensk, Serpukhov, Russia) (license no. 2020/10268 from May 08, 2020). Moscow mayor office has chosen Mindray system for wide screening to reveal COVID-19 convalescents in Moscow (Decision of COVID-19 Clinical Committee 2020). The decision was obviously non-evidence-based. To prove this, in the current Brief Communication we are presenting the results of our evaluating the three systems in question.

Mindray CL 1200i system is based on CLIA technology with proprietary portable detection device. Manufacturer specifies that their system detects *IgM* and *IgG* against specific antigens, recombinant N-protein and spike (S) protein, with 96.26% sensitivity and 95.38% specificity. Vector-Best VB SARS-CoV-2-IgM(IgG)-IFA-BEST and SRCAMB IFA anti-SARS-Cov-2 *IgG* test systems are ELISA tests, with the former based on whole virions (complete set of SARS-CoV-2 antigens) and the latter created to detect immunoglobulin *IgG* against SARS-CoV-2 nucleocapsid (N) protein.

The results of comparative evaluating sensitivity of the three test systems are presented in Figure 1. The overall evaluation methodology was conceived in accordance with COVID-19 Testing Project (COVID-19 Testing Project 2020; Whitman et al. 2020). The dependence of observed sensitivity on the time since onset (Figure 1, panels A and B) and virus amount (Figure 1, panels C and D) is given. Comparing sensitivity is of greater importance than absolute observed sensitivity values. Demographic and clinical course details are provided as Supplemental material. Virus amounts were estimated by RT-qPCR analysis, and all samples were SARS-CoV-2 positive.

Specificity evaluation results are presented in Figure 2, with false positive results coloured. Evaluation within randomized set is supplemented with sets positive for different acute respiratory infection (ARI) viral etiological agents. That may give an indication to which extent the assays studied are appropriate for SARS-CoV-2 population serological testing not only in summer 2020, but in times of future seasonal ARI surges. All serum/plasma samples were pre-COVID controls taken from epidemiological blood banks and collected no later than July 2019.

Vector-Best ELISA test kits were shown to be the most sensitive, while SRCAMB kit demonstrated highest specificity. Mindray CLIA system exhibited much worse performance, both in sensitivity and specificity – lower than claimed by manufacturer and measured in work of Nuccetelli et al. (2020). Favouring the Chinese system by Moscow mayor office for some political, financial or economic reasons not connected with epidemiological value, was a decision questioning the appropriateness of population testing results. Such administrative flaws have to be shunned in the future COVID-19 resistance, both in Russia and worldwide.

Worldwide healthcare/diagnostic community must not be pressed to comply with non-evidence-based governmental guidance. To outline a future social development in a post-COVID-19 time, only science may be a foundation for decision making, not arbitrary will of politicians.

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Fig. 1. Sensitivity of the three assays studied. A: Details of evaluating SARS-CoV-2 positive sample sets for antibody presence to SARS-CoV-2 antigens, by the three systems. Samples are subdivided into weeks since the disease onset. For asymptomatic carriers, no information on time can be provided. Coloured squares demonstrate positive results, uncoloured squares false negative results or samples where antibodies have not yet been synthesized in sufficient amounts to detect. B: Curves of dependency of observed sensitivity on time. Real sensitivity may be estimated by values for Week 4 and on. C: Dependency of observed sensitivity on SARS-CoV-2 amounts detected by RT-qPCR technique. D: Detailing of such dependency sample by sample. Greater virus amounts were detected to lead to greater amounts of antibodies.

Fig. 2. Specificity of the three assays studied. Uncoloured squares represent correct negative results, coloured squares false positive results. All samples are no-SARS-CoV-2 controls. Calculated specificity is provided to the right of each sample set.

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